

Supplementary Information
for
Spatially mapping thermal transport in graphene by an
opto-thermal method

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I. SUPPLEMENTARY NOTE 1: SEM IMAGE OF A TYPICAL SAMPLE AND RAMAN SPECTRA

FIG. 1. a) Scanning electron micrograph of a representative suspended graphene membrane. Arrows indicate defects (holes, contaminations, folds). b) Representative Raman spectra in the center of the same graphene membrane. The typical Raman bands, G and 2D, are labeled. The absence of the D-band indicates high graphene quality. The inset shows a histogram of fitted 2D-peak positions of Raman spectra obtained from a spatial 2D-mapping of the same device. The spread in 2D-peak position is attributed to different levels of strain, doping or defects.

Raman spectra are acquired with the following integration times per pixel:

2.135 s for 0.25 mW laser power

0.835 s for 1 mW laser power

0.331 s for 4 mW laser power

II. SUPPLEMENTARY NOTE 2: FINITE ELEMENT CALCULATIONS

A. Model

The FEM calculations were performed using Comsol Multiphysics 5.5. As shown in Supplementary Figure 2, the model consists of two concentric circles; the largest one represents the graphene on the support (R_{supp}) with a radius of $20 \mu\text{m}$, while the smaller one depicts the suspended graphene (R_{memb}), with a radius of $4 \mu\text{m}$. A third circle represents the laser spot (r_0) and is scanned across the graphene membrane. In Supplementary Figure 2, the laser is in the center of the suspended graphene. Within the entire domain, the two-dimensional, steady-state, heat equation in Cartesian coordinates is solved, as defined below:[1]

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\kappa(x, y) \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\kappa(x, y) \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} \right) = -Q - Q_{\text{laser}}(x, y) \quad (1)$$

where $T(x, y)$ [K] is the temperature distribution, $\kappa(x, y)$ [$\text{Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$] the thermal conductivity, Q [W] the heat losses via convection and/or the support, and $Q_{\text{laser}}(x, y)$ the heating due to the laser. The thermal conductivity of graphene on the supporting part is taken to be $1000 \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$, taken from literature[2]. As only boundary condition, a fixed temperature on the outer boundary of the support is used, set to the hot plate temperature.

For graphene on the support, the following heat losses are used to account for the interaction with the support and convection:[1]

$$Q_{\text{support}} = -g \frac{T - T_0}{t_{\text{gr}}} - h_{\text{conv}} \frac{T - T_0}{t_{\text{gr}}} \quad (2)$$

where T_0 [K] is the hot plate temperature, t_{gr} [m] the thickness of graphene (0.334 nm), h_{conv} [$\text{Wm}^{-2}\text{K}^{-1}$] the convection coefficient of air, and g [$\text{Wm}^{-2}\text{K}^{-1}$] is the interface thermal conductivity between the support and the graphene. For suspended graphene, only convection is present:

$$Q_{\text{suspended}} = -2h_{\text{conv}} \frac{T - T_0}{t_{\text{gr}}} \quad (3)$$

where the factor of 2 accounts for the convection occurring at both sides of the membrane. The thermal coupling to the substrate, as well as the convection parameter are taken from literature[1].

The laser is modeled as a Gaussian distribution, introducing a heat source equal to:

$$Q_{\text{laser}}(x, y) = \frac{Q_{\text{abs}}}{2\pi r_0^2 t_{\text{gr}}} e^{-\frac{(x-X_0)^2}{2r_0^2} - \frac{(y-Y_0)^2}{2r_0^2}} \quad (4)$$

where Q_{abs} [W] is the absorbed laser power, r_0 [m] the laser spot size, X_0 [m] and Y_0 [m] the laser position. Q_{abs} is calculated using $A \cdot P_{\text{laser}}$, where A is the absorption and P_{laser} the laser power. For the laser, a diffraction limited spot was used with a radius of 300 nm, and a cut-off of 2.5 μm , and a power of 4 mW. All calculation parameters can be found in Supplementary Table 1. Furthermore, a homogeneous absorption (A), defined by the fine structure constant $\alpha = e^2/hc$ giving $\pi\alpha \approx 2.3$ %, is initially assumed for the validation of the model [3].

When fitting the experimental data, a uniform absorption of 2.7 % is used, as determined experimentally, see Fig. 8. On the support, the absorption value is doubled to account for the absorption of the reflected light, as also done in literature.[4]

Experimentally, we do not only have a single laser spot position, but a rectangular grid containing the number of pixels in both spatial X and Y. For each laser spot position in the grid, the system was remeshed with the Comsol preset ‘extremely fine’ and the temperature distribution calculated. The average temperature within the laser spot ($r=185$ nm) was then used to construct the ‘temperature upon illumination’ map, equivalent to the temperature map obtained experimentally.

Now that we have explained how such a ‘temperature upon illumination’ map is obtained from a given thermal conductivity distribution, the next step is the reverse process, namely fitting/extracting the thermal conductivity distribution from a given ‘temperature upon illumination’ map. The starting point is an initial, uniform, guess of the thermal conductivity (1000 $\text{Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$). In each iteration of the process, the corresponding induced temperature map is compared to the experimental temperature map, after which the thermal conductivity is adjusted pixelwise according to the temperature difference. The following expression was used to adjust κ

$$\Delta\kappa = \text{sign}(T_{\text{calc}} - T_{\text{exp}}) \cdot 10^{\beta_\kappa \cdot \log_{10}(|T_{\text{calc}} - T_{\text{exp}}|)} \quad (5)$$

where $\Delta\kappa$ is the adjustment in κ . The β_κ -factor was set to 1.1. This expression was found empirically to improve convergence compared to a regular, ‘linear’ adjustment $\Delta\kappa =$

$$\beta_{\kappa} \cdot (T_{\text{calc}} - T_{\text{exp}}).$$

Finally, we note that it is challenging to model the transition from the suspended graphene to the supported graphene once the laser spot is in the vicinity of the edge due to 1.) reflection from of the laser excitation at the edges of the support may lead to an increase in the deposited laser power, 2.) quenching of the Raman scattered light on the substrate may lead to an overestimation of the local temperature as the 2D peak of the suspended graphene is more pronounced than that of the supported graphene. To circumvent this issue, the thermal conductivity of the first 0.5 μm of the membranes away from the support are not fitted. This was done by setting the values of $\Delta\kappa$ outside this area to zero, effectively keeping them and the initial value of $1000 \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$.

κ was converged for 100 iterations or until a minimum was reached, after which β_{κ} was set to 0. To improve the fitting of the experimental temperature map, the absorption A was then adjusted in a similar manner as κ using

$$\Delta = \text{sign}(T_{\text{calc}} - T_{\text{exp}}) \cdot 10^{\beta_A \cdot \log_{10}(|T_{\text{calc}} - T_{\text{exp}}|)} \quad (6)$$

Here, β_A was set to $1 \cdot 10^{-4}$ and the map converged for another 100 iterations.

We note that calculating the induced temperature map from the thermal conductivity map requires hundreds to thousands of individual COMSOL multiphysics calculations. To speed up to this process, we combined COMSOL multiphysics with the Parallel Computing Toolbox from Matlab. The Matlab LiveLink was used to generate the Comsol model from Matlab, calculate the temperature distribution for a given laser spot position, and extract the average laser spot temperature. Within a single ‘temperature upon illumination’ map, the Matlab Parallel Computing Toolbox was then used to send out the single calculations to multiple Matlab workers that execute the standalone calculations in parallel. The number of Matlab workers was set to the number of available cores. As the calculations are standalone, doubling the number of workers reduces the calculation time of a ‘temperature upon illumination’ map by two, provided sufficient memory is available. After all the single-thread calculations finished, Matlab was used to assemble the ‘temperature upon illumination’ from all the average laser spot temperatures and adjust κ or A accordingly. Then a new round of the single-pixel calculations were sent out again to the different Matlab parallel workers. This process was repeated until convergence.

The calculations were performed using Comsol 5.5 and Matlab 2019b, running on a

CentOS 7 workstation with a AMD Ryzen thread Ripper 2990WX CPU (3.0 GHz, 32 cores) and 128 GB of RAM (DDR4, 2933 MHz).

FIG. 2. Geometry used for finite element calculations. Graphene where suspended/supported is indicated by green/gray color respectively. The position of the laserspot is indicated with blue. The mesh used for finite element calculations is indicated with thin black triangles

B. Validation of method

We first validate our numerical method on a simulated system with a known thermal conductivity map, as shown in Supplementary Figure 3a. The thermal conductivity of the suspended graphene is set to $1000 \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$, while only $500 \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$ is used on the support.[2, 5] In the center of the membrane, a cross of low thermal conductivity values is defined. The temperature map upon illumination is also shown in the left panel, in which the cross in low conductivity values result in a cross of high temperatures. This temperature map will be fit using our iterative approach.

The procedure starts with a uniform distribution of the thermal conductivity. For each iteration, the induced temperature is calculated, as well as the error between the ‘experimental’ map and the calculated map. The error is used to adjust the thermal conductivity. For a series of iterations, the thermal conductivity, calculated temperature, and tempera-

Parameter	short	unit	value
Radius of suspended graphene	R	um	3.5
Radius of supported graphene	R_{supp}	um	8
Radius of beam spot	r_0	nm	185
Thickness of graphene	t_{gr}	nm	0.353
Laser power	P_{laser}	mW	4
Absorption	A	%	2.3
Ambient temperature	T_0	K	298
Convection coefficient graphene to air	h_{conv}	$\text{Wm}^{-2}\text{K}^{-1}$	2.9e4
Interface thermal conductance between graphene and Au/Si3N4 substrate	g	$\text{Wm}^{-2}\text{K}^{-1}$	2.8e7
COMSOL Multiphysics adaptive mesh	-	tetrahedral	1

TABLE I. Parameters used in finite element calculations

ture error are shown for two different given thermal conductivity maps, equivalent to two different defect distributions in Fig. 3 and 4. The convergence plot of the mean temperature error is shown in panel c).

In Supplementary Figure 3, for increasing number of iterations, the original Gaussian distributed thermal conductivity map is steadily recovered, with an maximum error below $10 \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$ when neglecting the part of the membrane within $1 \mu\text{m}$ of the support edge. In Fig. 4, the same procedure is repeated, but now with in the thermal conductivity map a cross with rounded edges. Here, after the fit procedure is converged, the cross shaped area is recovered, although some artefacts are visible. Here the maximum error in thermal conductivity stays below $50 \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$. We attribute these artefacts to the convolution of the thermal conductivity map with the Gaussian beam distribution. These artefacts becomes more prominent when the feature size in the thermal distribution map is comparable to the laser spot size.

FIG. 3. Demonstration of iterative calculation procedure in order to obtain a map of the thermal conductivity of defect engineered graphene with a Gaussian profile of defects across the graphene membrane. a) Input values. b) Results after specified number of iterations of the numerical fit. c) Mean error during the numerical fitting procedure.

FIG. 4. Demonstration of iterative calculation procedure in order to obtain a map of the thermal conductivity of defect engineered graphene with a cross of defects across the graphene membrane. a) Input values. b) Results after specified number of iterations of the numerical fit. c) Mean error during the numerical fitting procedure.

C. Gaussian vs uniform beam size

FIG. 5. Constructed temperature map upon illumination for comparing a Gaussian and uniform beam profile.

D. Spot size dependence

FIG. 6. Influence of spot size in calculations.

E. Mask size

FIG. 7. Comparison between a mask of $3.5 \mu\text{m}$ and $4 \mu\text{m}$.

III. SUPPLEMENTARY NOTE 3: ABSORPTION, LASER SPOT SIZE AND LASERPOWER

A. Absorption and Laser spot size

The FEM calculations also required as input the absorbed laser power and the laser spot size. Due to the complete suspension of the graphene film, measuring the transmitted laser power is performed by placing a power meter below the sample while scanning across the graphene membrane. By subtracting the power meter maps obtained on a graphene membrane from the one obtained on an empty hole in the SiN frame a map of the absorbed laser power is obtained, as shown in Supplementary Figure 8a. This is done using $1 - T = A + R$, where T represents the transmitted, A the absorbed and R the reflected part of the light while assuming the reflected part being negligible due to the low optical cross-section. The absorption map shows variation over the graphene film, indicating that residues, folds, and defects can influence the locally absorbed laser power and hence the heating up of the graphene. However, some of these areas of low transmission may also result from a high local reflection. As we do not measure the reflected power, to avoid errors in the absorption, the thermal conductivity maps are fitted using a uniform absorption of 2.7 %, corresponding to the average value, for the suspended graphene as determined from the experimental map shown in Supplementary Figure 8a) and double that value (5.4 %) for the supported graphene.

Measurements were performed under ambient conditions by placing a power meter (Thorlabs, PM100D, equipped with a photodiode) below the sample.

B. Laserpower

FIG. 8. Absorption and Laser spotsize measurements. a) Absorption as a function of position. b) Gauss error function fit to measured laserpower at different positions while crossing the edge of the SiN frame to determine the Laser spot size.

FIG. 9. Laserpower and Absorption measurements. a) Correlation between set and measured laserpower before the objective. b) Measured laserpower at different positions in the experimental setup.

FIG. 10. 2D peak evolution for different laserpowers. Peakproperties extracted from Lorentz fit to the spectra. Spectra taken with a grating of 1800 g mm^{-1}

IV. SUPPLEMENTARY NOTE 4: RAMAN SPECTRUM OF DEFECT ENGINEERED GRAPHENE

FIG. 11. Average Raman spectrum of defect engineered graphene. a) Raman spectra of He⁺-ion irradiated suspended graphene. The inset shows the He⁺-ion doses on the membrane. b) Intensity ratio $I(D)/I(G)$ at different average distances between defects. c) Intensity ratio $I(D)/I(G)$ versus $I(D')/I(G)$ leads to $I(D)/I(D')$ of ~ 11.7 .

V. SUPPLEMENTARY NOTE 5: ADDITIONAL SAMPLE

FIG. 12. Thermal conductivity map based on fitted experimental data. a) Experimentally determined temperature map. b) Fitted temperature map. c) Fitted thermal conductivity map. d) Converged absorption map.

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